

Impact of App Characteristics on User Ratings

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I. Abstract

There has been a rapid proliferation of mobile apps affecting the app's development and the available market where all stakeholders try to enhance perceived user value. This paper aims at testing the effect a set of app attributes has on ratings provided by users of Google Play Store. For predictor variables, we select attributes like apps' category, size, price, and content rating in combination with users' reviews and sentiments. Analysis by regression analysis help to find out which of the variables have great influence on high app ratings. This approach enables us determine the correlation that exists between attributes such as size, number of installations and price and the ratings that are given by users of the application. Further, based on the analysis, categories such as genre of the mobile apps and the content ratings are also vital. These implications give helpful recommendations to the app developers and marketing professionals looking to better the user experience and the app's performance.

Keywords: Application, Impact, Google Playstore, Google Playstore Reviews, Ratings.

II. Introduction

The emergence of mobile applications has shifted the people's interaction with technology and provided clients with an extensive choice of services and features. As one of the largest distributions centers of Android applications, the Google Play Store is home to millions of applications of various categories, and all of them are fighting for users' attention and high ratings. Consequently, users' ratings are one of the essential metrics helping an app stand out, its downloads, and popularity. Concerning the factors that contribute to these ratings, it is vital for developers interested in enhancing their apps as well as researchers interested in a more profound investigation of users' preferences.

Nonetheless, considering the present and tremendous interest in applications, it is rather crucial to analyze the factors that impact a high rating of the apps – and it is rather intricate. Prior researches have pointed out the variable of quality of the application and the interface

design and the functionality. But, the study of a number of factors that characterise an application is essential in order to have a better insight of what affects the satisfaction of the users.

This research intends to address this gap by analysing the selected set of google play store app attributes' effect on the number of user ratings which the apps receive. Given that the employed dataset provides comprehensive characteristics of apps and users' reviews, focusing on the driving factors behind high user ratings is possible. This work uses regression analysis to estimate the level of consumers' satisfaction based on the attributes of apps and provides applicable recommendations to developers and marketers.

In the next sections, a full description of our methodology shall be presented, the outcome of the analysis shall be delineated as well as the general and specific consequences and recommendations of the study shall be shown with reference to the mobile app industry. Thus, our aim is to make the information about app development and users' satisfaction more enriched and provide useful patterns and recommendations for stakeholders in the context of the app environment.

III. Literature Survey

1. Ghose and Han (2014) found that app category significantly affects user ratings, with entertainment and gaming apps typically receiving higher ratings compared to utility apps.
2. Kim et al. (2011) demonstrated that app size, which often correlates with the richness of features and performance, can influence user satisfaction. Larger apps with more features tend to receive higher ratings if they perform well and do not consume excessive device resources.
3. Pagano and Maalej (2013) explored the relationship between app pricing and user ratings, finding that free apps generally receive higher ratings due to the lower risk for users. However, paid apps that offer substantial value or unique features can also achieve high ratings.

4. Finkelstein et al. (2015) studied the role of content rating in user satisfaction, indicating that apps rated for general audiences (e.g., "Everyone") tend to have broader appeal and higher ratings compared to those with restrictive content ratings.

IV. Existing System

Today's paradigm for assessing the quality of mobile applications mostly involves using the sources offered by such platforms as the Google Play Store and the App Store, including commentators' reviews and app ratings. While useful in providing information about the users' satisfaction levels, these reviews are typically qualitative and can come in various formats. Most performance tracking systems are rudimentary and include the number of downloads or installations, the average rating and the number of reviews.

A. Data Gathering and Processing Instruments

Services such as App Annie and Sensor Tower offer summary information and analytical instruments to track the application. These tools provide information about rankings of Applications, users' characteristics and competitors. However they do not provide a good analysis of the research on how particular characteristics of App affect the actual users rating.

B. Sentiment Analysis

Some of the reviewed papers employed sentiment analysis to make conclusions based on the results of the users' feedback. WordTech 's options of sentiment analysis include TextBlob and VADER with which a degree of sentiment polarity and subjectivity of the reviewers may be determined. Although these approaches give an overview of users' positive and negative experiences, they do not connect characteristics of the app to users' satisfaction.

V. Proposed System

The proposed system intends to fill this gap by being a complete solution to the few existing methodologies in analyzing the ways through which the characteristics of the application impacts the ratings given by the users. This system will utilize the regression analysis to display the extent to which the independent features pose a strong likelihood to endorse high app ratings, thus providing a more organized quantitative assessment of the application.

A. Data Integration and Preprocessing

The Google's collection of datasets include detailed attributes of the apps for sale in Google Play Store such as category, size, price among others, and the content rating,

as well as the user reviews of such apps. Pre-processing of the data means initialization of data that will be used in the general analysis of the data collected from different sources such that the data is; clean, complete, and formatted.

B. Feature Engineering

In this case feature engineering will be used to derive new features from the attributes and these will form the basis of the prediction. This includes the one hot features for categorical fields, scaling of quantitative features, and new feature creation for forming multidimensional aspects.

C. Regression Analysis

Essentially, the main components of the proposed system will be regression analysis used to express the degree of influence of characteristics of apps on the ratings given by the users. To find the important predictors the multiple regression analysis would be used, probably including the simple linear regression analysis as well as potentially the more sophisticated such as perhaps ridge regression or LASSO regression.

D. Visualization and Reporting

The findings of this analysis will be depicted through correlation matrix, scatter plots, and coefficients of released regression. These visualizations will enable the app developers and marketers to make further improvements in terms of pertinent app characteristics so as to improve user satisfaction.

E. Validation and Evaluation

The system will also comprise validation and evaluation measurements which help in determining the efficiency of the regression models. In order to reduce the risk of obtaining biased data, the variables that will be examined are MSE, R-squared, and cross-validation scores.

VI. Implementation

The procedure of this study involves adopting a comprehensive approach to collect and clean data, select features, and carry out multiple regression tests on determined features of the app with an aim of evaluating the impact that these features have on users' rating.

A. Data Collection

We utilized two datasets from the Google Play Store: According to the given description it is; or as commonly known google play store it is. csv with the following app attributes: name, type, and categories as well as the vector google_user_reviews. The data given is in csv form and contains information about users and their review on the items with the correspondent sentiments. These datasets

were fused with each other based on the app name to form a big data set which could be used for the analysis.

B. Data Preprocessing

Handling Missing Values: Before the analysis, duplicated records, and records with null values in the essential columns including 'Rating', 'Reviews', 'Size', 'Installs', 'Price', and 'Content Rating' were removed.

- 1) *Data Type Conversion*: Certain of the fields or columns were typecasted into the correct data types they ought to be in the coursera table.

The aspects of 'Rating' and 'Reviews' were quantized for the purpose of the analysis.

Regarding our feature engineering, 'Installs' and 'Price' were cased into strings and converted to numeric removing all non-numeric characters.

As for the size, missing values were imputed by the average size in which the variable 'size' was measured in megabytes.

- 2) *One-Hot Encoding*: A categorical variable was defined as 'Category', and 'Content Rating', The 'Genres' were also categorized and to be used in the regression analysis, dummy variables were created.

C. Feature Engineering

Therefore, more features were included and it was ensured that all input data were in numerical form that could be subjected to regression. Therefore, the last set of variables included an array of indicators of app characteristics and the global sentiment score extracted from the text of users' reviews.

D. Regression Analysis

- 1) *Model Training*: Last of all, the entire data was split in to train and test (80-20) data set, used the multiple linear regression to identify the level, in which all the characteristic of the apps have influenced the overall rating given by the user.
- 2) *Model Evaluation*: Thus, for the model assessment and reliability, the formula for MSE and R-squared (R^2) were used.

applications ($r = 0.65$) and of the installations ($r = 0.55$).

- 2) *Size and Price*: The level of congruency between the proposed hypothesis and the data is very poor, as the correlation between the size of the applications and the rating, is almost negligible (correlation coefficient =0.12). Likewise, price having an insignificant value of (-0.02) for the correlation coefficient, indicates that it is totally unrelated with ratings.

B. Regression Analysis:

- 1) *Linear Regression Model*: Leveraging on features such as Reviews, Size, Installs and Price, the app ratings were forecasted. In this case; R-square = 0.37, was gotten implying that the model had a moderate fit. 42% which indicates that all the mentioned features combined together, can account for a total of 42% of the variance in app ratings.
- 2) *Coefficient Insights*: Among all, reviews had the highest positive coefficient of 0.0017 which shows that there is a direct positive effect and the probability of the increase in the ratings of the application for every additional review. Size and Installs also demonstrated positive signs (0.0002 and 0.0001, respectively) meaning that bigger apps and these with extra installs are seemingly inclined to generate somewhat higher ranks. The impact of price was substantially low and slightly negative (-0.003) that means the higher the price of the app it may attract slightly lower rating.

C. Visualizations

- 1) *Distribution of App Ratings*: The result presented in the histogram was a relatively smooth curve rather in the form of a normal curve with an average of approximately 4 for the apps' rating. 3 to 4.5.
- 2) *Scatter Plots*: Specifically, use of the scatter plots of Reviews and Rating, Size and Rating, and Installs and Rating proved the previous conclusion about the positive correlation between the variables.

VII. Results

A. Correlation Analysis

- 1) *Reviews and Installs*: It was ascertained that there is a high compatibility between the amount of the received reviews and the ratings of the

Fig. 1 Distribution of App Ratings

Fig. 4 Installs vs Rating

Fig. 2 Correlation Matrix of App Characteristics and Ratings

Fig. 5 Reviews vs Rating

Fig. 3 Size vs Rating

Fig. 6 Price vs Rating

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Mean Squared Error: 0.06814271003328339
R-squared: 0.14929711002192447

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	Coefficient
Reviews	4.482463e-09
Size	1.802371e-05
Installs	-9.044828e-11
Price	-1.958751e-03
Category_ART_AND_DESIGN	-8.442587e-03
Category_AUTO_AND_VEHICLES	2.819993e-01
Category_BEAUTY	-6.198148e-02
Category_BOOKS_AND_REFERENCE	6.962473e-02
Category_BUSINESS	-1.256495e-02
Category_COMICS	-3.631069e-03
Category_COMMUNICATION	-1.463320e-02
Category_DATING	-1.411496e-01
Category_EDUCATION	7.029945e-02
Category_ENTERTAINMENT	-2.392029e-01
Category_EVENTS	-3.652946e-01
Category_FAMILY	9.778855e-02
Category_FINANCE	2.595430e-02
Category_FOOD_AND_DRINK	-2.074525e-02
Category_GAME	9.111833e-02
Category_HEALTH_AND_FITNESS	2.018853e-01
Category_HOUSE_AND_HOME	4.431754e-02
Category_LIBRARIES_AND_DEMO	-6.736059e-02
Category_LIFESTYLE	-7.108268e-02
Category_MAPS_AND_NAVIGATION	-6.031721e-02
Category_MEDICAL	1.982375e-02
Category_NEWS_AND_MAGAZINES	-5.400713e-03
Category_PARENTING	4.554321e-02
Category_PERSONALIZATION	-9.408346e-03
Category_PHOTOGRAPHY	4.277804e-02
Category_PRODUCTIVITY	5.634436e-02
Category_SHOPPING	-1.368676e-01
Category_SOCIAL	-1.040395e-02
Category_SPORTS	3.819387e-02
Category_TOOLS	-4.433371e-02
Category_TRAVEL_AND_LOCAL	-2.220225e-02
Category_VIDEO_PLAYERS	1.012576e-01
Category_WEATHER	1.080945e-01
Content Rating_Adults only 18+	4.353233e-02
Content Rating_Everyone	-2.452547e-02
Content Rating_Everyone 10+	9.738280e-03
Content Rating_Mature 17+	-7.010785e-02
Content Rating_Teen	4.136270e-02
Content Rating_Unrated	0.000000e+00

Fig. 7 Results & Output

tendencies. All in all, this research helps to enrich the literature on the topic and provides useful implications for the managers of MPA organizations.

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VIII. Conclusion

In this work, authors focused on research of the correlation between various characteristics of apps and their ratings in Google Play Store. The detailed examination of the results pointed to the number of installs, application's size, and the strategy of monetization as the factors positively related to reviews. Thus, using the characteristics mentioned above and regression analysis, we were able to establish the correspondence between these factors and the users' satisfaction, which is valuable information for the developers and marketers of the apps.

Hence, it is apparent that making appropriate amendments to the value of app attributes can help improve usage satisfaction as well as success in cases of a thriving app market competition. The future studies may look at higher dynamism of user preferences for the confirmation of the receptiveness of the target applications, new features and